

TITLE

System and method for selling project-based services application software

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Introduction:

Great application or service does not guarantee success because it depends on how do you present your software or digital offering to buyers? So here we are sharing some strategy by using them one can improve sale of application software.

Software, sold as a service (SaaS) is a multi-billion-dollar business, with new providers and solutions emerging all the time.

In the technology 4.0 era IT industries focused towards the human problems and try to resolve it in an easy way so the consumer would get the solution in all areas like health related issues, security, retailing, travelling and campaigning areas. By using this kind of software one can make there work easy and attractive.

Objective: there are many significant points but few are as follows

- To provide the software platform to the users like Gmail, Facebook.
- To maintain the data in digital form like Digilocker, Github.

Used methods for selling application software:

At any company there are various teams like marketing, selling and many more its up-to businesses type and it varies on strategies as they have opt to launch the product and its marketing as follows:

1. Presentation of software:

Whenever a company launch its product like a new application software or services to the users and consumers so at first company should know very well about their products and how it is efficient to the consumer accordingly structure the presentation appropriately

- Create a big bold statement for your product or services.
- Use the statistical analysis of the product and its price well in the form of graphical user interface chart like pie and bar.
- Highlight a common problem and then prove that your software can solve this problem easily so introduce it as a solution.

Make your presentation interesting and engaging with the help of storytelling technique.

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Describe the software well, how it is used, where it is available, how it is unique and supportive for work completion.

2. Unpaid Use:

According to market strategies most of the organization use this type of method to launch the product and services freely or unpaid so that consumer explore and use it well and if the user is satisfied with company products and services next he or she is ready to pay for the same and this is how company product increase more and more as j curve.

Traditional software vendors don't use this free trial facility for their users so at that time selling software was bit difficult. When you provide free trial to your customers it shows that you value your customers the most.

Beta test:

A great way to start marketing is to launch a beta product. It's a good way to learn before the real product is available. Create a beta version of your application or software and launch it once it is bug-free and fully functional. Many SaaS companies delay their release of product by continually changing features they want before releasing the first version. Once it's in usable and operational form, take it to market and let your beta users give you review and help shape the future of software. There are many benefits to opening the service in beta. There will be problems, errors, unnecessarily complicated user flows, malfunctioning and poorly written text. With the beta version, you tell users that the product is not finished yet so ask them to be patient with you.

4. Understand customer's pain:

As an entrepreneur in the Software as a Service (SaaS), you know that developing new products always takes a lot of time and money. It is a risky business. If you develop a product that doesn't sell, you may waste more time and money on rebuild it. However, product development doesn't have to be this way.

One of the best ways to create a SaaS product that sells is to start by identifying the pain points your customers are facing, and then provide a solution to these problems. This sounds easy but much more difficult than these simple words.

You need to understand what a pain points are, how to ask questions, and where to look for more information about your target audience, you can improve your chances of correctly identifying a

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point of need, and therefore potential business success. Utilize the power of Google and other online platforms and tools to identify the real cause or trouble.

5. Reliable cloud hosting:

The key challenge with SaaS is finding web hosting that is powerful and scalable enough to support reliable and secure access to software for large volumes of customers.

We need to dug deep into customer and expert opinions to find the best VPS and cloud plans that allows the scalability, speed, and control needed for SaaS hosting at reasonable cost.

The best SaaS service providers are as follows:

- Salesforce
- Acquia
- AWS
- Cloudflare
- DigitalOcean
- Google Cloud
- HubSpot
- InMotion Hosting
- Pantheon
- Parallels
- Wix
- Kaltura

6. Freemium approach:

This is a popular strategy of companies to make its product and services more attractive among the consumers to use it freely so that users can judge whether software is worth for them, when they want to get full access of that software means premium version of it then allow them to access premium features for an upgrade cost.

7. Strategy for branding:

We can brand the software through the campaigning at various platforms like social media, TV channels, print media.

back guarantee:

It is a very good practice to win the customer's faith through this strategy, if some one not happy with the service or product they may get back the money for the same.

9. Feedback:

It is a renowned policy and best practice at organizations to get the feedback of the product and services from the consumers.

11. Find potential clients:

We can find out the potential consumers through the various strategies like campaigning through the social media and mouth publicity, if someone is happy with our product definitely he or she will suggest to the others for the same.

12. Multi-channel marketing:

It is a process of using online and offline marketing communication channels to target and interact with your customers.

13. Customer support facility:

It is a process of organization to provide the facility or support towards the product to the consumers 24/7.

14. Comparison table for Product and services:

We will provide the detailed information and comparative study of the products with the comparison of our products so it would be easy to understand about the product and services to the consumers to take the decision.

Fig1. SaaS services

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Pros:

- Cost: it is cost effective
- Speed: it provides the high speed during uses
- Easy to use
- Time saving
- No maintenance requires by the user
- Reliable

Conclusion:

It has been stated that the system and method for selling project-based services application software in the present era are playing a vital role toward the consumer satisfaction in terms of the uses of the upcoming technology that are reducing the customer efforts and providing a drastically growth for the businesses. The defined methods and technology like cloud computing is providing the various types of services like 360⁰ services to the users.

References:

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